

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN PHARMACEUTICAL PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT :

The pharmaceutical sector uses artificial intelligence extensively. These days, the pharmacy industry uses a variety of AI founded on natural language processing (NLP) and machine learning (ML). In recent years, artificial intelligence has become increasingly important in clinical trials, drug development, drug discovery, and research. However, there are also certain obstacles to implementing AI in the pharmaceutical sector throughout all manufacturing and processing stages.

Keywords:

Drug discovery, Drug development, AI devices, Clinical trials, Genetic algorithms.

INTRODUCTION

Since 1956, artificial intelligence has existed. Over the past 50 years, it has advanced quickly. AI sensing machines will increase human potential in many areas. Artificial intelligence is said to be used in a wide range of computer science and operational research fields. Information gathering is a common definition of intelligence.

and use that information to solve complicated issues.

Humans will soon be replaced by intelligent machines in many sectors.

The John McCarthy coined the term in 1956 to refer to the branch of computer science that deals with human perspective.

with making computers act like people. Perceiving reason and doing action are made possible by the study of computation. Because of its importance in computation, artificial intelligence differs from psychology and from computer science in that it involves perception, thought, and behaviour.

Intelligence can be defined as follows: Perceive + Analyse + React.

It makes machines more intelligent and useful. It operates using artificial neurones (artificial neural networks) and scientific theorems (if then statements and logics). Computers are capable of mimicking human intellect actions. The study of mental abilities using computer models is known as artificial intelligence. Understanding and carrying out intelligent tasks like reasoning, picking up new abilities, and adapting to novel circumstances and challenges are all made possible by artificial intelligence [1].

HISTORY

The Logic Theory was created by Herbert A. Simon and Allen Newell. In 1956, the hypothesis was developed. According to forecasts, the revenue from the AI sector is expected to increase by up to ten times between 2017 and 2022, with Dartmouth College hosting the renowned conference. The market for natural language processing, which includes speech and voice recognition as well as text prediction, is expected to expand by 28.5% in 2017.

Artificial intelligence has had a challenging history since the 1950s. The idea that chess was a field for idealists started to shift in 1997 when IBM's Deep Blue computer upset chess champion Garry Kasparov. The US game show Jeopardy awarded IBM's new Watson supercomputer a \$1 million prize by 2011. Watson has since entered the healthcare and drug-development industries, including partnering with Pfizer in 2016 to speed up immuno-oncology drug discovery. IBM Watson, a cloud-based tool that offers medical lab reports and assists researchers in finding connections between disparate data sets through dynamic visualizations, was unveiled in December 2016 by IBM and Pfizer.

A system known as artificial general intelligence, or AGI, states that a computer is capable of intellectual conduct similar to that of a human being performing many tasks simultaneously. A more comprehensive According to one viewpoint, artificial intelligence can integrate observation, learning, problem-solving, and system adaptation. Additionally involved are linguistic thinking and logic.[3].

There are two categories of artificial intelligence:

1. Weak AI.
2. Strong AI.

1. Weak AI.

The concept of weak artificial intelligence is that machines act like intelligent beings. Weak AI demonstrates that machines are capable of thinking, speaking, and moving if they are designed to do so. For instance, the computer can play chess and move players on its own. Although the computer lacks the capacity for thought, it is actually programmed to always operate appropriately.

2. Strong AI:

The idea behind strong artificial intelligence is that robots would perform computations, consider them, and forecast the outcome in the future. For instance, IBM's "WATSO" artificial intelligence supercomputer. Therefore, there will undoubtedly be machines in the future—or perhaps humanoids—that can think and act more intelligently than people.

AI DEVICES

There are two sorts of AI devices. Machine learning (ML) techniques fall into the first group, whereas natural language processing (NLP) approaches fall into the second.

1. Machine learning (ML)

Another area of artificial intelligence that examines structured data Machine learning (ML) includes genetic, imaging, and EP data. In medical applications, machine learning techniques attempt to classify the features of patients or determine the likelihood of disease outcomes⁵. Given the massive volumes of information arriving from a range of sources (including patients, wearable technology, physicians and clinics, non-physician clinical staff, research and development, etc.), machine learning (ML) is a rapidly expanding trend in the health care business. Although wearable technology has been around for a while in different forms, the complexity and popularity of wearables such as fitness trackers and smart watches in recent years have led to far larger collections of Real-time, trackable, and assessable personal health data.

It can be applied to a number of health care objectives, such as better drug development and production, clinical trials and research, more accurate diagnosis and treatment of radiology and radiotherapy, the creation of more intelligent electronic health record (EHR) and health information exchange (HIE) systems, and the forecasting of epidemic outbreaks^[6.]

2. Natural language processing (NLP)

One form of artificial intelligence is NLP that transforms human language into a comprehensible and structured format that computers may utilize for a variety of computational analysis and other purposes. Human language comprehension is not innate in computers. Without additional training, they are unable to break down human sentences into their constituent nouns, verbs, and adjectives, let alone distinguish which noun an adjective refers to or understand the idea of negation. This data is therefore in an unstructured format. By passing text via an NLP engine—a program created to encode human language—NLP aims to overcome these shortcomings. The NLP engine produces a set of structured data that represents the input text's content and that computers can comprehend and use.

Among the several methods employed in artificial intelligence are neural networks, fuzzy logic, evolutionary computing, and hybrid artificial intelligence.

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs):**Biological Neuron versus Artificial Neural Network**

Fig.1: Comparison of functional similarities of Biological neurons and Artificial neural networks.

Neural networks have gained reputation between engineers and scientists in recent years, and they are among the best computing tools ever created. This is because neural networks have the capacity to mimic the brain's assimilation process. Even when given insufficient information, this network nevertheless makes decisions and draws inferences. Furthermore, at a very basic level, neural networks mimic the brain's creative process when it comes to adjusting to a new circumstance. The technology known as The ability of neural networks in the brain to recognise patterns is replicated by artificial neural networks (ANNs). An artificial neurone unit functions similarly to a single neurone in the brain in information from a variety of outside sources, processes it, and then decides what to do.

ANN uses analogs of adaptive biological neurons to mimic the biological nervous system. Artificial neurons and multiple processing units (PE) make up an ANN. The strength of the connections between each unit varies and is determined by weights or factors. The ANN simulates how the human brain functions and may realize scientists' long-held goal of creating machines with human-like cognitive abilities. By modeling data and identifying patterns for intricate multifaceted situations, artificial neural networks (ANNs) imitate the human brain's generalisation and learning mechanisms. The ability of an ANN model to make the relationship between independent and dependent variables more broadly applicable without the need for a particular mathematical operation distinguishes it from a statistical model.

Thus, Quantitative structure-activity relationships in pharmacokinetics using space analysis investigations and structure prediction in drug development are two examples of nonlinear issues of multivariate and multi response systems that an ANN excels at solving[9].

Fuzzy Logic:

Pre-clinical in vitro and in vivo research, lead optimization, and lead and target discovery are the first steps in the rigorous, drawn-out, and sequential process of drug discovery and design. In the past, computer science, electrical engineering, and electronics and communication engineering have used computational methodologies to tackle difficulties. However, the application of these methods today has altered the course of drug discovery and design during the previous 20 years. Artificial neural networks, fuzzy logic, genetic algorithms, genetic programming, evolutionary programming, evolutionary strategy, and so forth are some examples of these techniques. The science of reasoning, inference, and thinking that acknowledges and applies the real-world phenomena that everything is a matter of degree¹⁰ is known as fuzzy logic.

Fuzzy sets have unsharp borders, which is how they differ from classical set theory. Therefore, in fuzzy sets, the value lies between $0 < \mu \leq 1$, where μ is the membership function, whereas in traditional set theory, the value is either 0 or 1. Fuzzy inference is the most crucial aspect of fuzzy logic. Fuzzy set theory-based fuzzy inference systems are thought to be appropriate for handling a wide range of real-world issues that are complicated, ambiguous, and lack an understanding of the underlying physical laws. Fuzzy rule-based models, which use linguistically interpretable rules to model the interactions between system variables, are the most significant

application of fuzzy set theory. Particularly when expressing target properties for optimizations, fuzzy logic can be helpful.

For instance, a formulator may be aiming for a 200 s tablet disintegration time, meaning that any value below that has a desirability of 1 (i.e., 100%). However, contrary to what strict logic would dictate, a tablet that dissolves in 210 seconds is not completely unattractive and may instead be given a desirability rating of 0.9. The fuzzy set's fundamental steps in process modeling are as follows:

- Arrange the input and output dataset.
- Clustering the output set
- Map the fuzzy inputs to the output
- Identify the significant variables
- Use the rule base in inference¹¹

Evolutionary Computing

It is a generic idea for a number of computer methods that are based on natural evolution, i.e., the survival of the most suited and the mechanism of natural selection. Consequently, real-world problems can be resolved by evolutionary computation. "Genetic Algorithms"¹² are the most prevalent application of EC in medicine.

Genetic Algorithms

A genetic algorithm (GA) is a search heuristic used in artificial intelligence that replicates the course of natural evolution. This heuristic, which is also occasionally referred to as a meta heuristic, is frequently employed to generate practical answers to search and optimization problems^[13].

Fig.2:Gene comparing and pairing by using Genetic Algorithms.

They are stochastic optimization techniques that offer a potent way to carry out directed random searches in a vast problem space, such as those found in drug design and chemometrics. The fitness function and the genetic representation of solutions are two requirements for defining a genetic algorithm. Drawing a genetic model is the first step in solving any problem. The definition of a fitness function for the problem comes after the genetic representation. The fitness function¹⁴ varies depending on the problem. The initial population of solutions is created by randomly generating a number of individual solutions at the beginning of the Genetic Algorithm.

The population's size depends on the type of issue. There could be hundreds or thousands of distinct solutions in it. The fitness function for every population is assessed in the following. Population reproduction is the final stage. The next generation of the population is created in this step by applying genetic operators including crossover, mutation, and selection. A molecule is defined as an input to GA in drug design, and the molecule is coded using a binary string. The genetic operator is used to produce many of the solutions. Until a desirable solution is achieved, the best population is chosen and then used to create additional populations[15].

Hybrid Intelligent Systems

Fig.3:Hybrid Intelligent System.

Since each of the systems on the list has pros and cons, new artificial systems employ additional methods to boost their potential. Together, they enable a hybrid system that can leverage human reasoning processes, extract meaningful information from unprocessed data, operate with imprecise information, and learn to adjust to an unfamiliar and changing environment[12].

IMPORTANCE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

The primary problem facing the modern world is AI. People can learn about its accomplishments in a wide range of fields, including science, technology, art, and entertainment, on a daily basis. AI takes into account how computers or machines understand, make decisions, and navigate in novel circumstances. Computers can operate around the clock, without fatigue, without losing focus, without bias, and they can process a disproportionately larger amount of information in a given amount of time (the computer that beat Grandmaster Kasparov at chess was able to estimate 200 million moves per second). Additionally, unlike human knowledge, which vanishes after death, their information endures forever[12].

THE HUMAN INTELLIGENCE DIFFER FROM AI

The ability of computer-controlled devices, such as robots, to carry out tasks that are nearly or identical to those performed by humans is known as artificial intelligence. Here, artificial intelligence is used to create a variety of robots with human-like cognitive traits, behaviors, and the capacity to learn from past experiences. These robots can also sense, make predictions, and interpret specific situations. Nowadays, robotic technology is quite popular and has spread to many different fields, including companies, hospitals, schools, the military, music, gaming, quantum physics, and many more.

Artificial intelligence is an effective way to make computers and software manage robotic thought processes using expert systems that learn, behave intelligently, and provide users with useful advice. AI is generally defined as robotics' capacity or potential for decision-making, problem-solving, and reasoning. Furthermore, intelligent machines that analyze vast amounts of data that a human person is unable to handle are part of artificially intelligent technologies, or robots. As a result, robotics is taking up repetitious tasks that call for creativity and knowledge.

Moreover, artificial intelligence (AI) is the fusion of multiple technologies that allows robots to comprehend, learn, perceive, or perform human tasks independently. In contrast to human intelligence, which primarily focuses on multiple multitasking skills, artificial intelligence programs (robots) are designed for specific tasks like learning, acting, and understanding. Robots that simulate human behavior are typically the main focus of artificial intelligence tools. But however, Artificial Intelligence may fail out at some places due to differences in human brain and computers. In summary, Artificial Intelligence has the potential to emulate human character or actions.

Additionally, existing artificial intelligence is only partially created and lacks sophisticated learning capabilities; instead, it is instructed to act. Artificial intelligence will reach its pinnacle in this future, when robots will be able to perceive human emotions and behavior and adjust their programming accordingly[16].

CHALLENGES TO ADOPTION OF AI IN PHARMA

Even though AI has a lot of potential to revolutionize the pharmaceutical sector, adoption is not always simple.

Challenges that pharma companies face while trying to adopt AI:

- The technology's unfamiliarity: Because AI is still relatively new and obscure, it still appears to many pharmaceutical businesses to be a "black box." inadequate IT infrastructure, as the majority of currently used IT applications and infrastructure were not created or planned with artificial intelligence in mind. Even worse, pharmaceutical companies must upgrade their IT systems at great financial expense.
- Since the majority of the data is in free text format, pharmaceutical companies must take extra care to compile and provide the data in an analysis-ready format. One thing is certain despite all of these drawbacks: AI is already changing the biotech and pharmaceutical industries. Additionally, in 10 years, pharmaceutical companies will simply consider artificial intelligence to be a commonplace, daily technology[17].

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN PHARMA IS A GOOD IDEA

Innovation in the pharmaceutical industry can be accelerated through the use of technology. Artificial intelligence, or the creation of computer systems capable of carrying out tasks that often require human intelligence, such as speech recognition, visual perception, decision-making, and language translation, is the most recent technical accomplishment that springs to mind. According to an IBM estimate, as of 2011, the total amount of data in the healthcare area was approximately 161 billion gigabytes. Given the vast amount of data in this field, artificial intelligence can be very helpful in evaluating the data and providing insights that will aid in decision-making, saving human time, money, and effort—and ultimately saving lives.

Predicting the location and timing of an epidemic outbreak can be done with a reasonable degree of accuracy by analyzing social media activity, studying the epidemic's history, and applying machine learning and artificial intelligence.

In addition to the use-cases listed above, there are many more, such as:

Personalizing the treatment

Help build new tools for the patient , physicians etc.

Clinical trials research: utilizing predictive analytics to find trial participants via social media and medical visits[17].

LIMITATIONS

simplifying electronic records, which need to be cleaned first because they are disorganized and dirty across several databases.

openness: Customers need openness in the medical care they receive due to the complexity of the processes utilising artificial intelligence.

Data governance: medical records are confidential and legally accessible. The public's consent is crucial. Pharma firms have a reputation for being archaic and unreceptive to change. In order to provide the greatest care possible, we must eradicate the stigma.

BENEFITS AND ISSUES

- Utilizing partial data sets effectively,
- Rapid analysis of data,
- The capacity to create rules that are easy to grasp and to take preferences and limitations into account,
- Improvement of product performance and quality at a reasonable price,
- A quicker time to launch,
- Development of new products,
- Improved customer response,
- Improved confidence¹⁹
- If properly coded, AI would have a lower mistake rate than humans. They would have
- Incredible precision, accuracy, and speed.

- Capable of doing risky duties,
- Travel through space and face challenges that could hurt or even murder us.
- This may even entail excavating and extracting fuels that are ordinarily inhospitable to people.
- Replace workers in tedious, repetitive activities and labour-intensive environments.
- Forecast the type, question, search, and action of a user. They can suggest or guide a variety of acts and can serve as helpers with ease.
- They are able to make logical conclusions with few or no errors since they are emotionally detached from their thoughts.
- Can assess people.
- This may be done for medical reasons, like emotional states and health hazards. can provide information on adverse effects and mimic medical treatments.
- Future surgical techniques, including robotic radio surgery, can attain precision that is unattainable by humans.
- Since they are not bored or exhausted, they do not require sleep, rest, breaks, or entertainment.
- The cost of building, rebuilding, and repairing it can be high; robotic repair can be used to cut down on the amount of time that humans must spend fixing it, but this will require additional resources and money.
- Although storage is vast, connections in memory may not form as easily as they would in people due to access and retrieval.
- This may make it difficult to empathize with feelings for interpersonal interactions, such those of nurses. This may also lessen knowledge and insight.
- This may hinder the application of common sense. They appear to struggle to acquire as much common sense as humans, even if they are taught it.
- People may become overly reliant on AI and lose their mental faculties, as is currently partially the case with smartphones and other technology.
- In the wrong hands, machines can quickly result in destruction. In other words, many people are afraid of it.

APPLICATIONS OF AI

AI is being used not only for disease diagnosis, tracking, and prediction, but also for the creation of novel medications.

Fig.4: Roles of Artificial intelligence in Discovery of drug. Drug design

It is predicated on tracking the interactions between target locations (enzymes, receptors) and 3D models of chemicals, which may indicate potential therapeutic targets. Deep learning based on the molecules' current behavioral history is used to accomplish this. In other words, AI creates possible medications according on how the molecules in its base behave, much like it does when it learns to recognize photos by examining hundreds of examples of images. Together with academics from the natural sciences, many programming businesses have developed an algorithm that identifies drug interactions with a wide biological system before focusing on more specific groupings of activities.

It also highlights how tens of millions of examples have been tested, producing predictions that are incredibly precise and fast. And that is exactly the secret to ensuring that medication research is successful, mainly because AI can more quickly analyze all conceivable combinations and narrow down potential actions[21]. Costs can be significantly reduced and In a few weeks, scan results will be available . A virtual hunt was started last year to find safe, already-approved medications that may be modified to treat the Ebola virus. The company's AI system has identified two medications that potentially dramatically lower the virulence of Ebola. It took less than a day²² to do this analysis, which typically takes months or years.

Drug discovery

A common phase in the drawn-out medication discovery process is testing compounds against samples of sick cells. To determine which compounds are physiologically active and deserving of more research, more analysis is required. Research teams at Novartis use images from machine learning algorithms to determine which untested chemicals might be worth further investigation in order to expedite this screening procedure. In addition to lowering the operating costs involved in the manual examination of every compound, computers can unearth new data sets significantly faster than conventional laboratory and human analysis tests, allowing for the earlier release of new and successful medications[19].

The following are some of the main AI projects being undertaken by biopharmaceutical companies: [a] a mobile platform to enhance health outcomes, which includes collecting data in real time to improve patient outcomes. [b] Drug discovery: In the expensive and The lengthy medication discovery process, pharmaceutical corporations and software companies are attempting to apply the most advanced technologies[23].

In Formulation

1. Controlled release tablets

Neural networks were first used by Hussain and associates at the University of Cincinnati (OH, USA) to simulate drug compositions. Numerous studies anticipated the in vitro release characteristics of several drugs dispersed in matrix composed of various hydrophilic polymers. Neural networks with a single hidden layer were shown to perform rather well in all circumstances when it came to drug release prediction. Overall, the outcomes were similar to those produced by statistical analysis; however, performance suffered when predictions that went beyond the parameters of the input data were made.

The idea of computer-aided formulation design based on neural networks was proposed by the researchers as a result of the results obtained, even though no attempt was made to improve the formulations using genetic algorithms. More recently, researchers from the University of Ljubljana (Slovenia) and the pharmaceutical company KRKA dd (Smerjeska, Slovenia) employed neural networks to predict the rate of drug release using two- and three-dimensional response surface analysis and optimise the formulation of diclofenac sodium from a matrix tablet made from cetyl alcohol. It is possible that many compositions with identical release characteristics might be produced, as non-linear relationships between the quantity and the release rate of the chemicals employed in the formulation were discovered.

Fig.5: Plasma concentration time profile for Intravenous and Oral or Subcutaneous administration.

2. Immediate release tablets:

About three years ago, two studies were carried out in this area. Turkoglu and associates from Cincinnati University¹¹ and the University of Marmara (Turkey) used neural networks and statistics to model the compositions of hydrochlorothiazide tablets. The networks produced in an attempt to maximise tablet strength or select the best lubricant were used to create three-dimensional graphs of massing time, compression pressure, and crushing strength or drug release, massing time, and compression pressure.

Although trends were noted, no perfect formulations were offered. The patterns resembled those generated by statistical techniques. Similar neural network After models were developed, they were optimised using genetic algorithms. The limits imposed on the levels of ingredients used in the formulation, and the optimal formulation was determined by the relative weight assigned to the output parameters. The only method to get a high tablet strength and minimal disintegration time was to friability. Lactose was utilized as a diluent in every instance, and the preferred granulating method was fluidized bed[25].

In Product Development

The development of pharmaceutical products is an optimization issue with multiple variables. It entails process and formulation variable optimization. One of the most advantageous features of artificial neural networks is their ability to generalise. Because of these characteristics, they can be used to solve Problems with formulation optimisation in pharmaceutical product development. ANN models showed better fitting and prediction capabilities in the creation of solid dosage forms in investigations of the effects of several elements (such as formulation and compression parameters) on tablet characteristics (such as dissolution). ANNs offered a practical tool for creating medication delivery systems based on microemulsions with the least amount of experimental work.

The phase behavior of quaternary micro-emulsion-forming systems made up of water, oil, and two surfactants was predicted using artificial neural networks (ANNs). In order to apply this kind of technology in the assessment and design of pulmonary drug-delivery systems, ANN was also utilized to model aerosol behavior. Fuzzy logic is a very effective problem-solving method for controlling and making decisions. From input data, it generates highly helpful rules in the style of "if... so... then." Neuro fuzzy logic is the result of combining fuzzy logic with neural networks. This combination gives the method greater adaptability and power while producing top-notch outcomes[24].

Clinical trials

Drug clinical trials are expensive and time-consuming, and machine learning offers a number of practical potential uses in assisting with trial organization. Testing can become more efficient and cost-effective by applying sophisticated, predictive analysis to identify clinical trial candidates, determine the ideal sample size for increased efficiency, adjust for variations in patient recruitment sites, and use electronic medical records to minimize data errors.

For enhanced security, machine learning can also be utilized for remote monitoring and real-time data access; for instance, tracking biological and other signals for any indication of participant harm or death[12].

Epidemiology

The history of the epidemic can be examined, social media activity can be examined, and the location and timing of the outbreak can be accurately anticipated with the use of AI and machine learning. With a precision of 86.37%, the AIME-AI Project in Medical Epidemiology and its platform provide three-month advance forecasting of the precise geographic location and date of infectious disease epidemics, such as zyka or tropical fever. Epidemic breakout has been discovered to be influenced by 270 modifiable variables. An autonomous system was created that automatically cycles through 270 variables every 23 seconds.

Fig.5: Statistical prediction of data in Epidemiology Market based on Artificial Intelligence.

Robot pharmacy:

UCSF Medical Center uses robotic technology to prepare and track pharmaceuticals in order to increase patient safety.

They assert that 3,50,000 medicine dosages have been effectively created by the technology. In terms of size and accurate drug distribution, the robot has proven to be more advanced than humans.

The robotic technology's capabilities include the ability to prepare injectable and oral medications, including deadly chemotherapy agents. The UCSF nurses and pharmacists now have more latitude to apply their knowledge by focussing on directly caring for patients and working with the physicians [17].

Pfizer, Roche, Novartis, Johnson & Johnson, MSD Merck & Co., INC., Kenilworth, N. J., USA, Sanofi, Abbvie, Glaxosmithkline (GSK), Amgen, and Giled Science are the top ten pharmaceutical companies that use AI.

Fig.6: Pharmaceutical industries using Artificial Intelligence.

The following areas of artificial intelligence (AI) were covered in this review.
 Diagnosis of disease; customized treatment using digital therapy:

Cancer, radiation therapy, retinal damage, and other long-term conditions.

Finding new drugs:

forecasting toxicity and bioactivity;

Clinical trials:

Trial monitoring, patient adherence, and endpoint detection; clinical trial design, patient identification, recruitment, and enrollment.

predicting a pandemic or epidemic

2. AI in the Diagnosis of Disease : 2. AI in the Diagnosis of Disease

Disease analysis becomes essential for creating a thoughtful treatment plan and ensuring patients' well-being. Human error makes it difficult to provide an accurate diagnosis, and misreading the information produced makes the work more difficult and time-consuming. By providing appropriate assurance in accuracy and efficiency, AI can have a wide range of applications. Following a thorough review of the literature, reports on the use of different technologies and approaches for disease diagnosis have been made. According to a variety of environmental expressions, the demand for the healthcare system is constantly rising as the human population grows [17].

The development of new methodologies can define the applicability by depicting the current existing scenario that has not been covered, despite the existence of vulnerable, contradictory, and non-analyzing incongruities, according to a large amount of data [18,19,20]. Patients should be categorized according to how badly their diseases impact them, and AI can become more significant in diagnosis [21]. A diagnosis is the point at which a person's condition is determined based on certain pre-existing issues [22]. In order to gather the majority of reviews that are received from conducting tests and examinations, it is usually recommended to keep track of each patient's health report forms. The suitable results of information gathering mostly relate to the medical requirements for an early diagnosis.

The analysis may change and is entirely at the clinicians' discretion [23]. One should prioritize AI for identifying and determining the early prediction stage of the disease above the treatment or diagnostic phase because the availability of numerous diagnostic methodologies is creating trust concerns. Such a diagnosis can aid in the start of early therapy, which can result in both enhanced AI module efficiency and observable changes in the patients [24, 25]. These days, there is a lot of technology based on deep learning, neural networking, and algorithms to identify, extract, and cater all the collected data [26,27,28,29,30].

Cancer and dementia are the two major diseases where AI has gained importance [31,32]. Algorithms can never be biased if they are not self-generated or have never been associated with any existing data. For statistical supervision, a relevant and specific dataset is required [33,34,35]. The acceptance lies not on the input from the user but the salience of the identified clusters [36]. Hepatitis can be diagnosed through unsupervised learning [37]. However, deep learning correlations can be obtained through various evolutionary changes and adjusting predictions [38,39]. Larger data sets and a variety of entries can typically support AI's applicability [38, 40], but the results are incomprehensible [41, 42]. Atrial fibrillation detection [44] and dermatological illness classification [43] are two of the numerous instances of deep learning in diagnostics. For the estimate of algorithms, cross-validation can be utilized for random splitting into different sets [45]. Three crucial areas are the focus of standard AI measurements: accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity [46, 47].

Based on the literature review, the results can be produced in a more comprehensive manner by the clinical aspects that can oversee the deep learning network and neural pathways using support vector machines, nearest neighbors, random forests, decision trees, logistic regression, naive Bayes, discriminate analysis, and convolution neural networks. The origin, sample size, and number of features of the training and testing samples can all be used to conduct algorithm-based performance-driven analysis. Decision trees and reasoning were combined to diagnose liver disorders [48]. Numerous experiments were conducted on predictive modeling, which showed promise in predicting Parkinson's disease early on. In order to diagnose lung illnesses, a rib segmentation algorithm was created utilizing chest X-ray pictures [50]. Due to a number of drawbacks, traditional techniques are not helpful for rib-wise X-ray image segmentation. In this study, an algorithm was created by augmenting chest X-ray images of patients with pneumonia using unpaired samples. A multi-scale network then learns the image attributes. According to the study, this algorithm performs well with improved rib segmentation, which may help identify lung cancer and other lung conditions [50]. Recently, algorithm and machine learning was used by the researchers in identification and classification of cardiac arrhythmia by processing the electrocardiograms signals. [51]. In another study, tuberculosis was classified and diagnosed by using the optimization genetic algorithm (GA) and support vector machine (SVM) classifier [52].

3. AI in Digital Therapy/Personalized Treatment :

AI has the capacity to extract a significant association from the raw datasheets that may be applied to the disease's diagnosis, management, and prevention. Nearly every area of medical science could benefit from the application of several more recent methods employed for computational understanding in this developing subject. The task of gaining, evaluating, and using a wealth of knowledge is necessary to tackle the complicated clinical problems (Figure 1). The advancement of medical artificial intelligence has aided physicians in resolving challenging clinical issues. Healthcare professionals can alter data with the use of technologies like artificial neural networks (ANNs), fuzzy expert systems, evolutionary computational systems, and hybrid intelligent systems [53].

The organic nervous system is the foundation of the artificial neural network (ANN) [54]. Neural networks, which are networks of interconnected computer processors, are capable of processing data in parallel. A binary threshold function was used to create the first artificial neuron [41]. With many layers, including input, middle, and output layers, the multilayer feed-forward perceptron was the most widely used model. Links with numerical weight are used to connect each neuron [55].

Figure 7. AI in acquiring and analyzing data of a patient in personalizing the treatment

In 1974, Paul Werbos presented "Backpropagation learning," a novel approach with an appropriate learning algorithm [56]. Waveform analysis, data interpretation, and diagnosis picture analysis have all made use of the ANN. The science of reasoning, inference, and fuzzy logic is capable of identifying and applying real-world events. Its primary membership is continuous, ranging from 0 to 1, where 0 denotes false and 1 denotes true. Vasodilators and anesthetics have also been administered in operating rooms using fuzzy controllers [57]. The natural evolution process, which emphasizes survival of the fittest, is the foundation of our evolutionary computation method [58]. The genetic algorithm is the most often used algorithm. It generates a large number of random solutions for a single problem, selects the best one, and eliminates the others [59].

3.1 AI in Radiotherapy :

One new technique that is very helpful in radiation treatment planning is automated treatment planning. The quality, consistency, and error rate of the plan are being effectively improved by automated treatment planning. Three types of treatment workflows can be distinguished: multi-criteria optimization, reasoning modeling of prior knowledge in clinical practice, and automated rule implementation [60]. The clinical guidelines can be implemented using a basic structured automated computer application. In addition to analyzing the patient's anatomy and physiology, the treatment planning system can replicate the thought process typically used in manual therapy planning. Promising accuracy has been demonstrated using three-dimensional dosage distribution and dose models for spatial dose [61]. Radiomics uses a number of imaging biomarkers to provide detailed information about malignancies. Radiomics can be used to predict radiation therapy outcomes and toxicity for specific patients [62].

3.2. AI in Retina :

Retinal high-resolution imaging has made it possible to evaluate human health in a remarkable way. With high-definition medications, the ophthalmologist/retinologist can construct a personalized therapy and create a continuously improving learning healthcare system using highly individualized data extracted from a single retinal photograph [63].

3.3. AI in Cancer :

AI's broad range of applications has made it more significant in the diagnosis and treatment of different types of cancer. A multilayer perceptron neural network was used to predict the lymphoma subtypes of non-Hodgkin lymphoma based on gene expression data. The input layer of the neural network consists of 20,863 genes. Using gene expression data, an artificial neural network was utilized to find new prognostic markers of MCL. It was found that 58 genes accurately predicted survival, while 10 genes were linked to bad survival and 5 genes to favorable survival [65]. Four genes were shown to connect with favorable survival and three with bad survival for DLBCL, according to the Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) using multivariate analysis of gene expressions [66]. The overall survival and prognosis of patients with follicular lymphoma (FL) were predicted using MLP and radial basis function (RBF) neural networks. Following an analysis of 22,215 genes, it was found that 18 genes were linked to a bad prognosis, whereas 43 genes were linked to the prediction of overall survival [67]. Using the genetic and transcriptional data acquired by RNA-Seq in the next-generation sequencing (NGS) platform, an AI deep learning technique was used to classify DLBCL according to its cell-of-origin (COO). AI produced assays for categorization and additional clinical use that were repeatable, effective, and reasonably priced [68]. AI is used to diagnose cancer with great accuracy and minimal time. AI-based PET imaging for lymphoma is used to assess tumor burden, which is then utilized to characterize the tumor, quantify heterogeneity, and forecast how well a treatment will work [69]. Colorectal cancer (CRC) screening technology is utilized to assess the malignancy in patients with gastrointestinal cancer [70], and visual nocturnal detection of *Helicobacter pylori* infection is essential for forecasting the advancement of gastric cancer [71]. The course of the malignancy can be influenced by early detection using appropriate blood tests, endoscopic imaging, and artificial intelligence [70]. However, only retrospective evidence can be collected because AI lacks blindfolded controlled research and appropriate randomization [72]. Additionally, in certain instances, the prediction models were unable to support the cancer prognosis. Subsequently, other models have gained several dimensions and likely predictive outcomes, including the random survival forest algorithm, Cox survival regression algorithm, and multi-task logistic regression algorithm [73]. These developments have made it possible to automate the diagnosis of cancer through gastroenterology, not only for categorization but also for endocytoscopy-based detection and magnification, which has not yet been applied in actual practice [74]. AI is a flexible clinical tool for screening and early diagnosis of lung cancer. Because deep learning and machine learning AI approaches can accurately describe pulmonary nodules and preserve large amounts of data, they provide a helpful metric in lung cancer screening [75,76]. AI now makes pathologists' jobs easier and helps distant institutes that are experiencing a pathologist scarcity. Numerous AI applications, including the segmentation of carcinoma foci, the detection of lymph node metastases, the counting of tumor cells, and the prediction of gene changes, have been found to be beneficial in the field of lung cancer [77,78,79,80]. Low-dose computer tomography (LDCT) pictures used for lung cancer screening may be interpreted by AI, improving diagnostic precision and lowering the false-positive rate [81,82]. Additionally, AI can measure morphological changes associated with and unrelated to tumors, which is crucial for serial imaging prognostication. The categorization of benign and malignant nodules can be distinguished using the convolutional neural network (CNN), recurrent neural network (RNN), and integrated dual effect of the two techniques [83]. Tools that are easy to use and don't require a foundation in computational science are essential to the advancement of AI in pharmaceutical and medical research in order to get beyond its limitations in translational research. AI has shown great promise in the diagnosis of breast cancer within the past ten years. Combining quantitative and qualitative MRI data, AI-assisted approaches can be used to predict treatment response in patients with breast cancer even prior to the initiation of neoadjuvant chemotherapy (NAC). AI holds promise for breast cancer risk assessment, breast density evaluation, and lesion recognition, segmentation, and classification. AI-based software can help radiologists differentiate between benign and malignant breast lesions and lower the likelihood that false-negative mammograms will be interpreted [84,85,86,87]. The progress in this area is still in its early stages and has several drawbacks, including the lack of sizable public datasets, the need for high-quality photos, reliance on ROI annotation, issues with binary classification, and the incapacity to manage several jobs concurrently. Because there aren't enough public data sets available to train deep convolutional neural networks (DCNNs), the development of AI tools, such as DL-based CAD, is still in its early stages [88].

3.4. AI in Other Chronic Diseases :

Various computer programming techniques have led to the development of various computerized therapies. The behavioral and cognitive method, which uses joysticks or multiple-choice questions, is the main focus of the therapy [89]. Intelligent computer-assisted instruction is a new type of computer interaction that has emerged recently. It can potentially use other AI technologies, such as expert systems and natural language understanding [90]. AI can also be used to develop a combination therapy based on the patient's own biopsy and to recommend n-of-1 medications. Regular monitoring is necessary for chronic diseases, and virtual medical assistants can be used to carry out this monitoring with AI.

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3.5. AI in Prediction of Bioactivity and Toxicity :

The affinity for the target protein or receptor determines the effectiveness. The medicine and target are considered to interact with the same target in a similarity-based interaction [109]. The drug-target interactions are predicted by Chem Mapper and the similarity ensemble technique [110]. Additionally, the substructure, connectedness, or both may be taken into account [109]. Since deep learning is not influenced by the 3D protein structure, deep learning techniques have demonstrated better performance [110]. The methods include predicting interactions between drug molecules, proteins, and deep affinity [111]. To avoid harmful impacts, the forecast is essential. Preclinical investigations are conducted after the in vitro assays, which are often preliminary research. This allows for additional improvement and allows for the differentiation of deadlines. To reduce the cost, a number of Web-based technologies are available [105]. The National Institutes of Health, Environmental Protection Agency, and US Food and Drug Administration conduct the Tox21 Data Challenge, which evaluates computer methods for estimating drug toxicity [105]. While eToxPred was used to estimate the toxicity of tiny compounds, an algorithm called Deep Tox outperformed all other methods by identifying both static and dynamic elements within the chemical descriptors. The guilt-by-association theory is used by TargeTox, a biological target-based pharmacological toxicity prediction [112]. The properties of the novel compounds can be predicted with the use of a scoring function. ProCTOR could predict with ease if a drug's toxicity would cause it to fail clinical trials. Adverse medication effects were also acknowledged [113]. . By anticipating the protein structure, AI can contribute by taking into account computation, geometry, and evaluation in conjunction with structure-based drug development [114]. To comprehend its usefulness and effectiveness, one must know the likelihood [114]. Issues with QSPR can be resolved by a variety of computational tools [115]. In order to achieve a positive feedback loop, decision-support tools employ rule-based choosing systems that rely on the kind and control of the quantity of additional ingredients [116]. Manufacturing systems are attempting to impart human knowledge to machines in response to the growing complexity of improving product efficiency and quality [117]. The pharmaceutical sector may benefit from the combination of manufacturing technology. The new platform is used by Chemical Assembly to implement automation [97].

4. AI in Forecasting of an Epidemic/Pandemic :

A pandemic has no limits and can result in both morbidity and death. The Black Death, Spanish flu, cholera, influenza, AIDS, and COVID-19 are just a few of the pandemic epidemics that have occurred worldwide and have the potential to disrupt social and economic life [127]. Early disease identification and effective management are closely linked, as they lessen the strain on people's health as well as on the political, social, and economic structures. Surveillance is crucial to achieving early detection [128]. Active surveillance requires a significant amount of time, labor, and resources. Epidemic and pandemic prediction is difficult in practice. But because of recent developments, it is now possible to examine the spread of terrible diseases. The greatest way to accomplish monitoring while making effective use of resources is with artificial intelligence. Many healthcare sectors are implementing machine learning and deep learning because they are more efficient than human resources [129]. The intricacy of epidemiological models continues to make their development difficult. Models for predicting outbreaks have recently been developed using machine learning [130,131,132]. AI is being applied to pandemic and epidemic detection, prevention, response, and recovery. It is starting to be widely utilized in prevention for information, surveillance, and prediction, particularly in light of the most recent COVID-19 outbreak [133]. Because of its fluctuating epidemic peak, periodic peaks, etc., influenza epidemic forecast is always extremely difficult. Even in regions with erratic seasonal influenza, a reliable forecast can be made by incorporating the SAAIM (self-adaptive AI model) [134]. For instance, Taiwan has employed ensemble and machine learning techniques to anticipate seasonal influenza, and the results show that the forecast is accurate [135]. The predicting output precision for influenza using the machine learning feed-forward propagation neural network model (MSDII-FFNN) is 90% [136]. In Australia and the United States, machine learning anonymised mobility maps, or AMMs, have been used to forecast influenza. Even across state lines, AMM can forecast epidemics using human movement by grouping data from smartphones [137]. Ebola is still a problem in Africa. Many methods have been used to forecast Ebola, such as a hybrid neural network created by Umang Soni et al. that exhibits 100% accuracy when random forest is used as a classification method [138]. Reliable results in propagation prediction have been achieved by the merging of machine learning and experimental models using artificial societies. For instance, a virtual model of Beijing has been used to study the spread of Ebola and anticipate the results [139]. Due to the lack of accurate forecasts, allocating surveillance resources during the 2015 Zika outbreak was extremely difficult. Later, the spread was predicted using a dynamic neural network model. During the early stages of the epidemic, this adaptable predictive model framework was dependable and beneficial [140]. The Zika research used a mobile application to track the number of mosquitoes, and AI neural networks were used to detect them early [141]. The observation of vaccine-derived poliovirus (VDPV) has drawn attention due to its results. The whale optimization algorithm (WOA) and random vector functional link (RVFL) networks are combined with hybrid machine learning to predict a VDPV outbreak [142]. ML can be used to identify probable candidates for pre-exposure prophylaxis in HIV/AIDS prevention strategies [143]. In tropical and subtropical regions, dengue is common. Support vector regression (SVR), an ML method, can follow dengue outbreaks in China and provide predictions with very little error [144]. The best dengue predictor in Malaysia was the ML Support Vector Model (SVM) with a linear kernel [145], while Bayesian network ML approaches were used to forecast dengue outbreaks [146]. Using TB suspect data, the ANN is integrated for quick diagnosis; its total effectiveness exceeds 94%. This will facilitate the prompt implementation of some control measures and the detection of the disease's overall spread [147]. A CNN model called tuberculosis AI (TB-AI) demonstrated 97.94% sensitivity in identifying TB bacteria through the use of deep learning and machine learning [148]. A prediction accuracy of 88% was attained by the Multilayer Perceptron Neural Network Classifier (MPNN), which was proposed for the diagnosis of yellow fever using seven psychological symptoms of the illness [149]. The world was rocked by the COVID-19 outbreak [150]. The COVID-19 was predicted using improved stacked auto-encoder modeling inspired by AI [151]. Fuzzy rules combined with deep learning Composite Monte Carlo (CMC) was useful for making decisions and forecasting the COVID-19 pandemic [152]. To forecast with minimal error, a polynomial neural network with corrective feedback (PNN + CF) is employed [153]. CNN, a Chinese deep neural network, is effective at making accurate predictions [154]. In Switzerland, COVID-19 is predicted using the AI model (Enerpol) in conjunction with big data [155]. Statistical and deep learning systems, including feed-forward neural networks (FNN), multilayer perception (MLP), autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA), and long short-term memory (LSTM), were used to examine the dynamical behavior of COVID-19. The generated data could serve as a helpful guide for the COVID-19 forecast [156].

Fig 6 Application of AI in various stages of Drug Developm

Conclusion

The most advanced machine that can never be made is a human. The human brain is putting a lot of effort toward creating something that can perform any activity significantly more effectively than a human, and it is somewhat successful in doing so. The pharmaceutical industry can use technology breakthroughs to speed up innovation. The latest advancement in technology that springs to mind is artificial intelligence, which may truly assist in data analysis and result presentation to aid in decision-making while saving human labor, time, and money—and ultimately, lives. The field has seen significant development as a result of AI tools like robotic pharmacies. Artificial intelligence is the development and application of algorithms for learning analysis and data interpretation.

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